

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****A STUDY OF RELATIONSHIP OF DEPRESSION WITH THE
SMOKING STATUS AMONG OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT
PATIENTS IN DISTRICT LAHORE****Dr. Zeeshan Majeed¹, Dr. Ghazala Afzal², Dr. Sheraz Khan³**¹Medical Officer in Pak Red Crescent Teaching Hospital, Lahore,
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sherazstar46@yahoo.com.**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: The high co-occurrence of smoking and mental illness is a major public health concern, and smoking accounts for much of the reduction in life expectancy associated with mental illness. 1 Many studies report a positive association between smoking and mental illness, with smoking rates increasing with the severity of the disease. 2,3 Individuals with mental illness also tend to start smoking at an earlier age, smoke more heavily, and are more addicted to cigarettes than the general population.

Methodology: Setting: This study is conducted at psychiatric clinic of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore.

Sample size: the total sample size estimated using 95% depression patients 250, 5% margin of error with an expected percentage of smoking. 7%.

Sample Selection: Consecutive non-probability sampling

Study Design: Descriptive cross-sectional study

Results: Among smokers this Incidence of depression percentage was 52.2%. While 47% of Ex-smokers 47% were depressed (p-value = 0.903, nonsignificant)

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Please cite this article in press Zeeshan Majeed et al., A Study Of Relationship Of Depression With The Smoking Status Among Outdoor Department Patients in district Lahore , Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07[07].

INTRODUCTION:

The high co-occurrence of smoking and mental illness is a major public health concern, and smoking accounts for much of the reduction in life expectancy associated with mental illness.¹ Many studies report a positive association between smoking and mental illness, with smoking rates increasing with the severity of the disease.^{2,3} Individuals with mental illness also tend to start smoking at an earlier age, smoke more heavily, and are more addicted to cigarettes than the general population.

International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10) classifies Depressive disorders or 'episodes' as mild, moderate or severe, with or without somatic symptoms. Among the individuals with severe depressive episodes, presence or absence of psychotic symptoms can help further differentiate the affected population. Depressive disorder, clinical or 'major' depression, indicates depression, regimen, speech, energy disorder and frustration. Symptoms should end at least 2 weeks and cause a significant inability to understand the illness (e.g. trouble working or relating to others) [4].

Depression is the main cause of the global burden of disease and the second leading cause of years lived in disability (YLD) in 2010[2]. Women and Adults of working age group are more affected. Whilst Global disease burden has increased by 37.5% between 1990 and 2010. Approximately 15% of the population and 6–8% of all outpatients fulfill the diagnostic criterion for depression. However often it is left undiagnosed. Male to female ratio is 1:2 [5]. Depressive syndromes are defined in Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-IV) diagnoses major depressive disorder if when more than five of the below mentioned conditions are present more than 2 weeks. These conditions have to be present more most of the time of the day, every day [6].

- **Emotional symptoms:**
 - o Depressed mood*
 - o Loss of interest / pleasure in most activities*
- **Neurovegetative symptoms:**
 - o Loss of sleep or excessive sleep
 - o Alteration in appetite or weight (5%)
 - o Psychomotor retardation or agitation
 - o Low energy
 - o Diminished ability to think or concentrate
- **Ideational symptoms:**

- o Thoughts of worthlessness or guilt
- o Recurrent thoughts about death or suicide

Although the public health burdens of tobacco-related disease and mental disorders appear to be linked,⁷ the cause-versus-effect relationship is difficult to clarify given the complex molecular effects of nicotine on the brain. Some studies⁸ have suggested that depressive and anxiety symptoms were associated with smoking initiation. Conversely, other recent studies have indicated that smoking may contribute to the development of these conditions.⁹ Furthermore, several studies have shown a link between smoking and suicide risk¹⁰. Notably, in a logistic regression modeling study, Hallfors and colleagues found that being a smoker was a strong independent predictor of suicidal ideation. Because a female gender bias for internalizing behavioral symptoms (e.g. depression, anxiety/intense worry, somatic symptoms) is well documented in adolescents,¹¹ we investigated whether this bias would be reflected in our findings and if so, if there would be any relationship to tobacco use.

METHODOLOGY:

Setting: This study is conducted at psychiatric clinic of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore.

Sample size: the total sample size estimated using 95% depression patients 250, 5% margin of error with an expected percentage of smoking.7%.

Sample Selection: Consecutive non-probability sampling

Study Design: Descriptive cross-sectional study

Data Collection

250 patients visiting psychiatric clinic for their depression follow up will be included per criteria in study after taking informed consent. After selection of patient study Performa will be filled by me. After inquiring all the questions from Beck's depression inventory II scale, final score will be allocated to each patient according to respective responses.

RESULTS:**AGE DISTRIBUTION**

Between June 2014 and December 2014, 250 patients visiting attending psychiatric clinic at Jinnah Hospital Lahore Patients with age ranging 18 years to 60 years with mean of 42.82 and standard deviation of 11.65. Histogram below shows this pattern as majority of the patients were within 30 years to 60 years of age.

Graph1: Age distribution of Depression patients

Table below shows that majority of the depressed population belonged to non-smoker group among whom 55.8% of the nonsmokers were depressed. Whereas among smokers this percentage was 52.2%. While Ex-smokers 47% were suffering from some sort of depression. 74 out of 172 nonsmokers were suffering from mild clinical depression and moderate depression with 37 each in both groups, however p-value was 0.903 which made this finding inconclusive.

Beck Depression Inventory - II Score	Smoking Status			Total
	Non Smoker	Smoker	Ex-Smoker	
Normal (BDI - II score Less Than 17)	76	21	18	115
Mild clinical depression (BDI- II score: 17 – 20)	37	9	5	51
Moderate depression (BDI- II score: 21 – 30)	37	11	7	55
Severe depression (BDI- II score: 31 – 40)	10	2	1	13
Extreme depression (BDI- II score: over 40)	12	1	3	16
Total	172	44	34	250

Table 1. Relationship of smoking status with Depression,P-value = 0.903 (of table above)

Among smokers this Incidence of depression percentage was 52.2%. While 47% of Ex-smokers 47% were depressed (p-value = 0.903, nonsignificant)

			Smoking Status			Total
			Non Smoker	Smoker	Ex-Smoker	
Depression status	Normal	Count	76	21	18	115
		% within Depression status	66.1%	18.3%	15.7%	100.0%
		% within Smoking Status	44.2%	47.7%	52.9%	46.0%
		% of Total	30.4%	8.4%	7.2%	46.0%
	Depressed	Count	96	23	16	135
		% within Depression status	71.1%	17.0%	11.9%	100.0%
		% within Smoking Status	55.8%	52.3%	47.1%	54.0%
		% of Total	38.4%	9.2%	6.4%	54.0%
Total	Count	172	44	34	250	
	% within Depression status	68.8%	17.6%	13.6%	100.0%	
	% within Smoking Status	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	68.8%	17.6%	13.6%	100.0%	

Table 2. Frequency of Depression with relation to Smoking status ,P-value = 0.625

Frequency and Severity of Depression

According to the Table below 54% of the smokers were diagnosed to have depression of some severity with majority of the population among the depressed lying between mild clinical depression and moderate depression i.e. 20.4% and 22% of the total 250 patients respectively.

Beck Depressive Inventory – II (BDI-II) Score	Frequency	Percent
Normal (BDI - II score Less Than 17)	115	46.0
Mild clinical depression (BDI- II score: 17 – 20)	51	20.4
Moderate depression (BDI- II score: 21 – 30)	55	22.0
Severe depression (BDI- II score: 31 – 40)	13	5.2
Extreme depression (BDI- II score: over 40)	16	6.4
Total	250	100.0

Table 3. Frequency and Severity of Depression

Graph 2. Pie chart showing percentage of patients who were depressed and in various stages of depression.

DISCUSSION:

Depression is a debilitating disease which if not diagnosed and treated in timely manner will lead to a more complicated course of other co-morbidities. This leads to increased mortality because of noncompliance to medications because of depression [11]. Once its diagnosed in a smoker population it always returns back on most times and are at high risk for relapse even with anti-depressants [12].

Its prevalence among the smoker's population of Pakistan ranges from as low as 14.7% to as high as 60% [13]. In our study this frequency came out to be 54% of the smoker.

In our study Incidence of depression steadily increased among smoker patients as their age increased i.e. 12 year – 19 was 1.5%, 20 year – 29 year was 11.1%, 30 year – 39 year was 21.5%, 40 year to 49 year was 27.4%, 50 year – 60 year was 38.5%. (p-value = 0.381) which could not be confirmed, perhaps we needed a larger sample size to confirm these findings. Perhaps age takes its toll along with other psychological stressors to increase the depression incidence in older population [14].

Prevalence of depression among the divorced were maximum of the 3 groups (single, married and divorced) which was 68% (p-value less than 0.01) which can be associated as a risk factor for development of depression in our population. Thus,

suggesting a stricter screening should be carried out for smokers who were divorcee [14].

Smoking couldn't be established as a risk factor for depression as it was evenly distributed among smokers and nonsmokers (p-value = 0.903). This is in contrast to international study according to which patients with depression are more prone to smoking. Diagnosis is made based upon clinical history and examination which involves interviewing the subjects him/herself and the account of their family members. Interview revolves around establishing presence of following:

- Psychiatric symptoms: These have been discussed above. Also determine their chronologic order, assess their functional status, and determine any aggravating factors
- Mental status examination: This is to detect presence of alterations in speech, psychomotor activity, mood and affect, thought processes, and suicidal thought content
- Medical history: specifically current and past medical history along with use of medications and systemic review

SCREENING

Following are well-established screening tools

Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS)[15]

It's valid for younger adults as well despite its name. Its 5-item version has 5 question and score of 2 is necessary to screen positive for a patient. Its sensitivity ranges from 50% to 97% with median of

85%. While specificity is from 51% to 98% with median of 74%.

Patient Health Questionnaire - Nine Item (PHQ-9)

The PHQ-9 establishes the clinical diagnosis of depression, and does not require further confirmation. It has 9 questions which are given score and can be categorized into mild, moderate, moderately severe and severe depression.

Beck Depression Inventory for Primary Care (BDI-PC)[15]

It has 7 questions from the extensively validated 21-item Beck Depression Inventory. The score of 4 points out of 7 establishes diagnosis of major depression. It has 97% sensitivity and 99% specificity.

Beck Depression Inventory – II

It contains 21 questions given in annexure-I, with each option scaled at value of 0 to 3. Based on cumulative score it categorizes depression into following states based on severity:

- 0–13: minimal depression
- 14–19: mild depression
- 20–28: moderate depression
- 29–63: severe depression.

It has sensitivity (87%) and specificity (79%) for screening depression [119].

These individuals should be referred to a proper mental health facility as it was detected in meta-analysis screening/case-finding interventions alone has no or minimal impact management, or outcome of depression by clinicians in general settings [120].

Laboratory evaluation

These may include Complete blood count, Serum electrolytes and glucose, Serum urea and creatinine, Liver function tests, Thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), Screening for syphilis, Serum B12 and folate, Urine routine examination. Electrocardiogram may be done to find a source of possible embolic cerebral infarct, and MRI brain for clinically occult vascular or mass lesions.

CONCLUSION:

Depression is seen 54.4% of the smokers. Majority of smokers suffered from mild to moderate depression. Based on this prevalence, we can recommend that every smoker should be screened for depression at least once while being managed for lung diseases due to smoking.

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